

Design activism as a new method for inquiring into mixed emotions in uncomfortable social interaction

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Abstract Over the last couple of years, design activism has attracted increasing attention among designers and design researchers, but the approach seems not to have found its way yet to the Design & Emotion research community. In this paper, we introduce design activism as a new approach valuable for probing into the role of mixed emotions in interpersonal interaction. To set the scene, we critically examine recent sources on design activism in order to provide a general characterisation of what constitute the approach. Next, we argue for how social game can be seen as an instantiation of design activism used, in a current research project, to inquiry into how teenagers feel about visiting their incarcerated fathers in top secure prisons. Finally, we relate our findings to discourse on ambiguous emotions and use this to visualize the eliciting pattern of ambiguous emotions.

Keywords *Mixed emotions, Uncomfortable interaction, Design activism, Disruptions*

Introduction

Over the last couple of years, design activism has attracted increasing attention among designers and design researchers, but the approach seems not to have found its way yet to the Design & Emotion research community. This is unfortunate, because design activism offers a variety of practices, methods and techniques for addressing emotions in their socio-political forms of manifestation – forms that typically falls outside the explanatory scope of design and emotion research.

Design activism's value for emotion-driven design approaches can be identified on at least two levels. At a *macro-political* level, emotions are pivotal, for instance, for the release and configuring of conflicts, upheavals or riots that social movements perform to protest against systems of power, ideology and control. Here design activism has been proclaimed to be a valuable means for achieving benefits for the whole of society or even Planet Earth, for instance, by instigating more sustainable ways of living as an alternative to existing consumerist lifestyles (Fuad-Luke, 2009; Thorpe, 2012). At a *micro-political* level, the feeling of being wronged, discriminated or excluded is often motivating individuals to act in order to resist or modify negative power structures experienced by the individual themselves, their family or community. At this level, design activism has proved to be a useful approach, for instance, for empowering cancer patients to have a say in decision-making processes during their treatment at hospitals (Eva Knutz, Markussen, Mårbjerg Thomsen, & Ammentorp, 2014); for increasing citizen rights and participatory democracy in the shaping of the urban environment

(Markussen, 2013); or for integrating the needs of marginalized ethnic groups into the design of services of public institutions (Lenskjold, Olander, & Halse, 2015).

In this paper, we shall focus on design activism as practiced on the micro-political level. There are two reasons for this. First of all, the majority of studies on design activism have paid attention to the macro-political level. These studies tend to view design activist practices primarily in light of their underlying motivating political cause, notably the globally growing dissatisfaction with neo-liberalism's greed for growth and consumption, the resulting financial and economical crises and the negative impact on our environment (Fuad-Luke, 2009; Julier, 2013; Thorpe, 2012). However, at the micro-political level, we rarely meet conflicts that are determined by an overtly political disagreement. As a matter of fact, it can be fairly difficult in the first place to see that there even is a conflict. Politics, here, is a matter of how power is subtly interwoven into the way in which individuals, in their everyday life, are constrained by systems of authority and control. Therefore, the central questions are: How is people's ability to act, feel and communicate regulated by these systems of power? How do these systems configure roles of identity, and determine who has the power to speak, move and work. Systems of power can be found in the form of public institutions and services (healthcare, education, work) or they can be materialized into physical form as when public furniture is designed to prevent certain societal groups to use them (e.g. homeless and alcoholics). To fathom how designers can help vulnerable groups to escape the limitations and

constraints of power structures, it is necessary to develop an approach enabling them to work with these power structures as a design material that can be subverted, re-modified and transformed.

Our claim in this paper is that design activism represents such an approach, but we need to work out more concise definitions for understanding it. Hence, in contrast to the dominant views, we argue that definitions of design activism according to its political cause and motivation are insufficient. Instead, we suggest that a definition according to its *modus operandi* would serve as a more valid defining criterion. By *modus operandi* we refer to the particular way in which design activism is practiced through disruptions and provocations. To make our case, we start out, in the very beginning of the paper, by critically reviewing some of the current definitions of design activism. On the basis of this, we will then be able to present our alternative definition and how it contributes to the existing body of knowledge.

The second reason for focusing on the micro-political level is that design activism offers new methodologies for researching into mixed and ambiguous emotions. In the D&E proceedings series and elsewhere we have detected a growing interest in mixed emotions, ambiguity and even uncomfortable interaction. However, much of this research has been devoted primarily to developing conceptual frameworks and theory (see e.g. Benford et al., 2012; Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012; Fokkinga, Desmet, & Hoonhout, 2010; Gaver, Beaver, & Benford, 2003), while less attention has been paid to which methodologies are appropriate for investigating these complex forms of emotion in situ.

In this paper, we introduce what we shall call *social games* as a new activist methodology that enables design researchers to gain insight into mixed emotions as they appear in uncomfortable interactions. We have successfully used social games as a method to investigate the ambiguous emotions of teenagers, who are visiting their incarcerated fathers in top secure Danish prisons. As much research in sociology and criminology have made abundantly clear, in-visits programs in prisons are extremely important for the well-being of children and adolescents (see e.g. Beckmeyer & Arditti, 2014; Dunn & Arbuckle, 2002; Kampfner, 1995; Poehlmann & Eddy, 2013). However, what is not well recognized is that the children do not experience seeing their incarcerated parents as unequivocally positive. The happiness or joy of being reunited for a short while is often counterbalanced by negative emotions such as guilt, anger or fear. This is a key finding for developing future programs and visiting facilities.

Our social games have been designed so as to let teenagers play out their mixed feelings and emotions associated with visiting their imprisoned fathers. By drawing on our general reflections on design activism as well as recent theories on critical play and activist games (e.g. Flanagan, 2009) we will explain in more detail how social games can be understood as an activist methodology. In so doing, it will be feasible

for others, working in related areas, to value social games as a method for unravelling emotions in interpersonal interaction. Finally, we will discuss and conclude on how our findings concerning mixed emotions fit into existing frameworks and theory.

Related work on design activism and political design

Design activism is an emergent field that is gaining solid foothold in design research. This is not least evidenced by the proliferation of conferences and conference tracks, special journal issues and books dedicated to the topic. Initially, it might be worth considering how we should generally conceive of activism. According to Jordan (2002, pp. 8–11), activism can be defined as a group of “people acting together outside ‘normal’ institutional channels” in order to transgress and change existing state of affairs according to the desires of those taking action. As a further defining criterion, Jordan says, that “a *disruption* of the pre-existing morality-defining institution can be found” (Jordan, 2002, p. 10 our italics). Hence, we could think, for instance, of Occupy Wall Street as a vivid example of activism, where a group of people disrupts the institutions and capitalist power inhabiting Wall Street as part of a collective protest against social and economic inequity worldwide. However, we need to be aware that design activism is not the same as political activism. As we have argued elsewhere, design activism is not a boycott, strike, protest, demonstration, or some other political act. It “lends its power of resistance from being precisely a *designerly* way of intervening” into systems of power (Markussen, 2013, p. 38). The question is of course what do we mean by ‘designerly’? Let’s go through some recent suggestions to make our own notion stand out more clearly.

It is a widely held belief that design activism should be understood as opposing capitalism’s idea of free markets, consumption and economic growth being the pillars of society. Such a view can be found in Thorpe’s book *Architecture & Design versus Consumerism: How Design Activism Confronts Growth*, wherein she argues at length that design activism is about focusing on design’s social and environmental returns (p. 7), not on the marketplace and sales numbers. In Thorpe’s interpretation, design activism becomes a term that is interchangeable with designing for social innovation and sustainability. And design, for her is then primarily anchored “to physical, material and visual aspects of the built and manufactured environment” that live up to these criteria (ibid.)

However, we argue that Thorpe’s account is confusing. First, even though many design activists would perhaps agree with the agenda, it is unwarranted to use social and environmental sustainability as the essential defining criteria, because it risks confusing design activism with a motley assembly of other divergent practices. Thorpe’s own listing of exemplary activist work within architecture and design throughout the book clearly shows why this is problematic. If we take Thorpe’s definition at face value, Michael Reynolds’ Earth Ships (p. 9) would thus be as activist as Renzo Piano’s California Academy

of Sciences (p. 159). But, as we see it, only one of them qualifies as such, namely the Earths Ships.

Reynolds has revolutionized architectural practice by showing how people, living in areas hit by natural calamities, can rapidly re-build their houses and villages by using simple DIY-practices, garbage and found materials. In so doing, he has made these people independent of architectural companies, the good will of local policy-makers and emergency aid. Renzo Piano's California Academy of Sciences certainly deserves credit for its eco-friendly architecture, but it is not – like Reynold's Earth Ships – the outcome of a practice "outside 'normal' institutional channels". Nor does it show any sign of "disrupting pre-existing morality-defining institutions". On the contrary, it is part of the marketplace that architects nowadays have to respond to with 'sustainability' luckily entering the vocabulary of the client.

Secondly, Thorpe's idea of architecture and design being understood simply in terms of "physical, material and visual aspects of the built of the built and manufactured environment" is exactly what many design activists have problematized. For instance, Awan et al. (2011) argue that the equation *architecture=building* needs to be reformulated, because it represents the idea that a building or produced stuff is the solution to every social and environmental problem. Further, by prioritising aspects of static properties of objects, emphasis is put on visual, aesthetics and the technical, "over which architects still retain nominal control, in terms of being able to manipulate form and technique". In contrast, Awan et al. (2011) argue that architects need to see the loss of control as "an inevitable condition" and that architecture and design is part of a dynamic network of socio-political actors with divergent needs, interests and values. By replacing 'architecture' with the notion of 'spatial agency', the authors underline that the radically new task of architects and designers is to find ways of empowering spatial agents (minorities, citizen groups, communities, and so on) to appropriate public space independently of the constraining structures of society.

Within design studies, a similar critique of the equation *design=products* has been voiced, albeit not in strict activist terms, by Björgvinson, Ehn & Hillgreen (2012; 2010) and DiSalvo (2010, 2012). Björgvinson et al. raise concern that the idea of design being "a tool for the development of functional, innovative consumer products" is unable to appreciate the social-political complexity of today's problems. Instead they suggest conceiving of design as a political "infrastructuring", that is design as processes of change used to modify "the space of interactions and performances and that may be "explored as socio-material frames of controversies, opening up new ways of thinking and behaving" (Björgvinsson et al., 2012, p. 102). On the same note, DiSalvo introduces the term "adversarial design" to denote a design approach that acknowledges an underlying dissensus between agonistic interests and forces as a foundational condition for design in public space.

Following from these observations, it is necessary, as Fuad-Luke (2013) has suggested, to come up with some clearer definitions. According to Fuad-Luke, "The way that design activism levers political change depends upon whether the design approaches set about to encourage dissensus, consensus or both." (Fuad-Luke, 2013, p. 473) Design activism that encourages dissensus is "working outside or oppositional to the existing paradigm", while design activism that encourages consensus is "working within or inside the existing paradigm" (Fuad-Luke, 2013, p. 470). However, we suggest reserving the term "design activism" to denote only design work living up to the first definition. This definition is in line with Jordan's general characterization of activism and underlines that contest, subversion and disruption are at the core of design activism. The second definition is too vague, in our view, because it would apply equally to practices such as design for sustainability, social innovation, social entrepreneurship and social design. All of these fields are commonly defined in the research literature as working within or inside the existing paradigm in order to achieve social or environmental returns (see e.g. Manzini, 2014; Moulaert, 2009; Moulaert, MacCallum, & Hillier, 2013; Phillips, Lee, Ghobadian, O'Regan, & James, 2014). Consequently, it becomes impossible to tell the difference between design activism and these other related approaches.

Yet, what distinguishes Fuad-Luke's work from Thorpe's is that he derives the defining criteria of design activism from a closer scrutiny of its way of operating rather than its aim or motif. More specifically he highlights dissensus as being essential for its modus operandi. Interestingly, this bears some likeness to DiSalvo's (2012) notion of 'adversarial design' and Björgvinson et al.'s (2012) notion of Design Things (with a capital T). Both of which denote fields of design conditioned by dissensus, meaning controversies and agonistic forces. However, in their accounts, dissensus is reduced to be a matter of political dissensus, while aesthetic dissensus is neglected. Aesthetic dissensus, according to Rancière (2010) is when artistic practices, including design, are used to re-distribute sensible-material conditions so as to open up the relation between people's action, feelings, and emotions for renewed negotiation. It is the effect, for instance, of heterogeneous objects being brought into social-political space thereby enabling a redistribution of power, control and roles of identity. Reynold's Earth Ships provides a paramount example of aesthetic dissensus. In constructing the Earth Ships we see most literally how sensible garbage and waste materials are redistributed to become valuable building elements. By enabling people, with the use of DIY- techniques, to re-build their own houses the feeling of how they live and inhabit space is also fundamentally changed from negative to positive. Finally, architectural practice works as spatial agency to affect a redistribution of power and control, by emancipating marginalized people from being passive victims to become active citizens taking the spoon in their own hand.

What can be seen in examples like this is that dissensus in design activism deals with political issues, but notice that “stakes of politics”, as Rancière (2004, p. 13) says, are staged through an aesthetic practice as a form of experience. This is the hallmark of what we refer to as a ‘designerly’ way of practicing activism. It is a way that political power can be disrupted and contested through aesthetic practice thereby opening up new ways of living, thinking and communicating.

Social games as an activist research method

Working out more accurate notions of activism in general, and of design activism in particular is a prerequisite for understanding how games can be approached from an activist perspective. In this section, our aim is to demonstrate that not only can games be the resulting product of a design process. They can also serve as a research methodology for uncovering how mixed emotions regulate and shape uncomfortable interpersonal interactions at a micro-political level. Key to this methodology is disruptions and subversions that are able, through the game experience, to open up a gap, to be studied further, between actions, emotions and action tendencies. It is precisely in this sense that the notion of games we will be presenting here differs from what is commonly known as ‘design games’. Design games are usually found valuable as means for involving multiple stakeholders in collaborative processes of design (Bang, 2010; Brandt, 2006). Most often, such co-design processes aim towards the design of products, solutions or services, and the involved stakeholders have more or less clearly identified roles and identities (e.g. client, sub-providers, technicians, end users, designers, etc.). It is a matter of using games to arrive at consensus, to embrace a large degree of complexity defining design problems and to let people influenced by a design solution have a say in the developmental process. In the activist understanding of games, games are not means for co-designing solutions among stakeholders, but for re-negotiating the relations between the people involved and redirecting attention of the inquiry towards a possible re-configuration of these relations. For this reason, we prefer the notion of social games to design games (see also E. Knutz, Lenskjold, & Markussen, 2016).

Elsewhere we have provided a thorough introduction to social games being a rather unexplored object of study in design and game research (Markussen & Knutz, 2016). Hence, in this section, we shall only briefly account for what characterises social games and focus instead on how they can be used as part of an activist methodology. In the next section, we use empirical findings from a case project to further substantiate our argument and claims. This will eventually lead to the identifying of types of mixed emotions, which will be discussed in relation to existing research literature.

Social games are games that are designed to explore processes of socialization or the forming of interpersonal relationships. In social games, play can be used, as Sutton-Smith (1997) has convincingly shown, for the sake of transforming social bonds,

feelings of belonging to a social group or work out social and cultural norms. For the same reason, social games must be distinguished from related game genres such as *serious games* and *health games*. While serious games are designed to train and educate players in solving problems, acquiring new skills and knowledge (Michael & Chen, 2006; Shaffer, 2006; Squire, 2005; Westera, Nadolski, Hummel, & Wopereis, 2008), health games are designed to improve the well-being of the players, for instance to reduce anxiety in children after their parent’s divorce (e.g. *Earthquake in Ziiland*) or to help veterans suffering from Post Traumatic Stress disorder (Helms & Rahbek, 2012). The primary goal of social games is neither edutainment nor health improvement, but to build and negotiate social relationships between the players. This means that social development is the central game goal, and that a nuanced understanding of how play and game may be constitutive for interpersonal interaction is essential.

Another central difference between serious games and health games and social games has to do to with how the games either comply with or disrupt existing power structures. Serious games and health games typically affirm certain hierarchical orders and asymmetrical distributions of control characteristic of the organization and contexts they are designed for: The surgeon plays the role of a surgeon operating on a patient, the pilot play the role of the pilot navigating an airplane, and so on. In contrast, since social games are designed for the sake of overthrowing power structures, they often disrupt social identities by letting people play imaginatively with alternate identities, forbidden identities and even identity switching. For the same reason social games often use fictionalization rather than simulations as is the case with serious games and health games (E. Knutz, Markussen, Desmet, & Visch, 2012).

Within game studies, Flanagan has introduced the term “activist games” to account for “games that engage in social issues, through, most commonly, themes, narratives, roles, setting, goals, and characters; and less commonly, through game mechanics, play paradigms, interactions, or win states to benefit an intended outcome beyond a game’s entertainment or experiential value alone” (Flanagan, 2009, p. 13). More importantly, Flanagan further specifies that activist games always use tactics and elements of subversion and disruptions, that is actions or interventions intended to overthrow “a law, rule, system, condition” (Flanagan, 2009, p. 10). To see how social games can serve as part of an activist research method, it will be useful to look more carefully at how we have used social games in an on-going research project.

Case project: Social Games against Crime

One of the aims of the research project Social Games against Crime is to increase knowledge of how children and adolescents (age 11-18) experience visiting their incarcerated fathers in top secure Danish prisons. Relatively little is known about these children and statistics on their visiting frequency and patterns are sparse. Yet, there are indications that

Figure 1. Left: Signs standing on the parking lots. Right: a top view of how the players cars “drive” around to pick up helpers.

children stop visiting their fathers at the age of 10-11 for various reasons. This is unfortunate, because, as criminology and social research have demonstrated, the sustaining of a positive relation with an incarcerated parent may have a beneficial effect on how children are able to cope with the personal and social problems caused by imprisonment (see e.g. Beckmeyer & Arditti, 2014; Dunn & Arbuckle, 2002; Miller, 2006; Poehlmann & Eddy, 2013) .

In the present study, we will be focusing on teenagers of gang members (the project as a whole focus on a broader target group). Drawing upon the design activist framework we have introduced, it is possible to conceive of in-visits taking place in prisons as involving emotions eliciting on a micro-political level. Remember that, as we said in the introduction, on this level, politics is not about overtly political disagreement and conflicts, but has to do with the way in which authority and control is subtly interwoven into and constraining interpersonal interaction. Often, the effect caused by such constraints makes itself felt as a matter of mixed and uncomfortable emotions.

Having a father incarcerated has similarities with what is described as ‘ambiguity of loss’. Ambiguity of loss occurs when families live through grieving processes, for instance, because of the acute separation of a loved one, divorce, illness, war, terror, or death. According to Boss (2007, p. 105), ambiguity of loss may come in two variants. The first one is when a loved one is physically absent, but is felt as being psychologically present (e.g. this has been reported by relatives to military deployed abroad). The second form of loss is when a loved one is felt as being psychologically absent but is physically present (e.g. this has been reported by relatives to Alzheimer patients). Both forms are distressing, uncomfortable and may traumatize (ibid. 2007).

Children visiting their fathers behind bars are faced with the first condition of ambiguity of loss. Evidently there is more to it than what the physical-psychic

divide can account for. What is important is thus to understand the ambiguous emotions involved and how they play a role in the forming of social relationships between children and their fathers. What are the mixed emotions that children experience as part of in-visits interaction? We shall argue that social games can be a valuable new a method of inquiring into this complex set of questions. Initially, we will describe a social game that was designed as a research artefact to help the researchers know more about the mixed emotions of teenagers who have a father incarcerated for more than ten years in top secure prisons. Saying that the game is a research artefact means that it was designed as a playful form of participation for a target group with the purpose of collecting and documenting knowledge about their inner emotional life. Hence, the game elements were designed in different colours and materials to allow the researchers to backtrack the game process and gather data about each teenager’s individual relationships with their fathers.

Participants and procedure

The participants were three teenagers (age 14-16), two family therapists and two design researchers served as facilitators. The teenagers come from similar environments and their fathers belong to the same criminal gang. The game was used as part of a 2-day game workshop, held at a family consultation centre that offers help to families and children of inmates. The workshop was organized into two parts. In the first part, three teenagers and one family therapist played the game, whereas two teenagers and two family therapists played the game in the second round.

The game consists of a board with a winding road that takes the players round a city. On the road, there are eight parking lots, where the players can park their car to pick up helpers. The parking lots are: “The Treatment Centre”, “The Pub”, “The Tech Shop”, “In the Media”, “Personal Talents”, “On the Street Corner” and 2 “Family and Friends” (see Figure 1). There is also a cemetery where you end up, if one of the other players bumps into your car. Before starting the game, each

Figure 2. Left: Mira's dream and barriers. Right: Niels' dream and barriers.

player must formulate a wish or dream on a card that is then placed on "the Cloud", found on the centre of the board. Next, the players are given three "Barrier Cards" upon which they must write down three barriers that prevent them from fulfilling the wish or dream.

Each player has his or her own toolkit, where there is a "Dream Card" and a car, modelling wax, cotton balls and sticks so that the players can make their own character. The game play consists in throwing a dice to drive around the city and, on the way, pick up helpers who can help you to overcome your barriers. On the parking lots the players can find predefined helpers, but they can also invent their own writing them down on empty "Helper Cards". By throwing a yes/no dice the player determine whether an attempt to break down a barrier is successful or not. On the road there are a number of roundabouts. When landing on them the players must choose roundabout card that makes it more difficult to achieve the goal.

In the following we present our findings gained from playing with two of the teenagers. For the sake of data protection their identity have been blurred, using fictitious names.

Mira is a 14-year old girl. She starts the game by saying that she wishes to see her father less than once a week (the current situation). On her Barrier Cards she writes that it will be "difficult to tell him", that "he gets disappointed" and cannot see the situation "from her point of view". To overcome these barriers she mentions, when she lands on the "Family and Friends" spot, that she would like her father's friend Jacob to assist her when she is going to tell him that she does not want to come as often. Jacob is a former gang member, but is still highly respected by the father. When she lands on Personal Talents for the first time, Mira recognizes that she will need "better speech

gifts", the second time it is suggested – with a smile – by one of the other players that she could perhaps use "hypnosis" to convince him. (Figure 2)

During the play Mira shares with the family therapist and other teenagers that she is afraid, that when she tells her father that she will not come as often, he will call some gang members and ask them to break up her current friendships with other girls and boys. He knows that by disclosing that she is the child of an incarcerated father, many of Mira's girl friends would simply stop seeing her. Mira feels threatened and controlled, but at the same time that telling him is best for her well-being.

Niels is a 14-year old boy. For over a year, he has not been visiting his father in prison, because of a dramatic episode: the father was calling some gang members outside prison to have them threaten Niels' mother. But now Niels is slowly making contact again, because he wants to see his father. On his Dream Card he writes that he would like "more reasonable visits" (Figure 2). Asked about what he means by "reasonable" Niels says that he doesn't want to talk to his father about problems with his mum or the elder brother who is a drug addict. Reasonable to Niels is, for instance, when he fights with his father in the visiting room and they toss around chairs. Then, he really feels being close to his father; that his father is psychologically present and loves him.

On his Barrier Cards, Niels identifies three barriers that stand in the way of achieving the reasonable visit. His father is "unable to see when he is wrong"; "he doesn't understand why Niels says that he needs a break", and he's annoyed about Niels being accompanied by his foster father" (at the age of 14 children are not allowed access to prisons in Denmark without being accompanied by an adult). That makes things complicated.

Discussion

The game we designed for this project can be regarded as an activist method for at least two reasons. First of all, it makes visible the power structures and control that the fathers exert over their teenage children. Notably, this takes the form of threats of breaking up their relationships if the teenagers do not do as the fathers please. Secondly, while this certainly evokes negative emotions like fear and anxiety in the children, they also experience positive emotions when seeing their fathers. By playing the game the teenagers not only become aware of these emotional tensions; they also work out a set of strategies for how to re-configure the relationship with their fathers according to their own needs and wishes.

We can get a better grasp of this if we turn towards some general conceptualizations of mixed and ambiguous emotions. Fokkinga and Desmet (2012) have proposed four main clusters for describing mixed emotions, which are useful to accurately describe how emotions regulate the ambiguous relation of the teenagers with the fathers. Hence, they distinguish between mixed emotions manifesting themselves as in i) 'unrelated emotions' where positive and negative emotions are evoked by different situations or objects, and no mutual interdependency can be detected; ii) 'ambiguous emotions' occur when positive and negative emotions are elicited by the same situation or object; iii) positive effect of negative emotions is when negative emotions has a certain positive effect on either the person's experience of the situation, their attitude towards the situation or their behaviour, which in turn leads to a positive emotion; and iv) 'negative effect of positive emotion' is when positive emotions have a negative outcome. Due to limited space we will not go into each one of these clusters here. Instead, we will concentrate on how Mira's and Niels' social bonding with their fathers can be further explained as forms of ambiguous emotions.

For Mira the visiting situation evokes two opposite, yet closely interrelated emotions and action tendencies. On the one hand, the prospect of visiting her father to tell him that she will not come as often, is evoking anxiety and negative emotions, because she fears his threats and hence she feels reluctance to go and see him (action tendency 1). On the other hand, she feels torn, because she still wants to keep a good relationship with him and continue seeing him, just not as often. This is evoking a positive emotion and an action tendency 2, which is in contrast to the negative emotions. Using the diagram of Fokkinga and Desmet (2012) this can be depicted as in Figure 3.

In Niels' case, ambiguous emotions are also at stake in regulating how he relates to his father and the prospect of visiting him again. Niels is experiencing negative emotions of the visiting situation when recalling his father discussing problems about his mother and brother with him (stimulus). Previously he has shown that if he feels too much pressure he will actually stop coming to the prison (action tendency 1). Yet, at the same time Niels is eager to change this situation so that he gets reasonable visits in the future, perhaps he can fight with his father, which he

Figure 3. Ambiguous emotions as identified in Mira's and Niels' stories. Adapted from Fokkinga & Desmet (2012).

feels very positive about (action tendency 2). Like in Mira's case this is causing ambiguity between two opposite emotions and action tendencies.

Fokkinga and Desmet's framework is useful for explaining not only mixed emotions, but also how they are involved in configuring uncomfortable interpersonal interaction. Thus, the object evoking ambiguous emotions can be a person, a situation or the relationship between two persons. In this sense Fokkinga and Desmet's framework contribute with a dimension that is absent from some other existing frameworks found within Design and Emotion. For instance Markussen (2009) identified ambiguous emotions being central for understanding the use of technology in healthcare, but here ambiguous emotions were analysed as a tension between mentally elicited and embodied emotions not as a result of social interaction. Earlier we have introduced a distinction between fictional and real emotions in order to account for how a computer game could be used to help small children cope with the ambiguous emotions they live through when being hospitalized (E. Knutz, 2012, 2013; E. Knutz & Markussen, 2010). But again, in this account, the social dimension of emotions was left out of attention.

Interest dedicated to mixed emotions has also appeared in HCI and interaction design. Gaver et al. (2003) pointed out years ago that ambiguity could be a resource for design in the sense of designing "products and systems to become psychological mirrors for people, allowing them to try on new identities or to question their values and activities". But in Gaver et al. (2003) ambiguity is most of all a matter of conceptually challenging effect being narrowly

conceived of as a relation between people and products and systems, not as a social relationship between people. The same is the case with Benford et al. (2012) who have argued that “deliberately engineering discomfort”, can be “a way of creating intense and memorable interactions and engaging with dark and challenging themes” (Benford et al., 2012, p. 2005). In Benford the social is only conceptualized as rites de passage, processes where the individual go through critical transitions to become member of a group. Yet, the teenager’s visiting their father is not about them going through a rite de passage. They engage in dark and challenging themes, but they struggle to figure out whether they should continue seeing him. It is a different concern.

Interestingly, however, what both Gaver and Benford call attention to is that ambiguity and discomfort may have a similar effect as dissensus and disruption. They open up for a new formation of identities (Gaver) and for engaging with dark and challenging themes (Benford). In our social game these effects result from activist elements of the game. Thus, it is allowing the teenagers to untie the bond between their actions (visiting) and how they feel about these actions. In so doing, a more fine-grained view can be gained of what exactly is causing the feeling of uncomfortable interactions.

Conclusion

In this paper we set out initially to provide a more concise definition of design activism. After providing a critical review of some of the existing literature on design activism, we suggested that design activism could ideally be seen as a design practice evoking dissensus and the overturn of pre-established macro- and micropolitical structures. By defining it according to its modus operandi, we argued that it is possible to distinguish design activism from the closely related disciplines such as social innovation and social entrepreneurship. Secondly, we exemplified how social games can be seen as an example of an activist methodology taken in the sense that these games may disrupt entrenched roles of identity, the habitual coupling of action and emotions, saying, doing and feeling. The value of such a methodology hopefully became evident in our account of how the social game could be a viable way of probing into the nature of ambiguous emotions. Thus by playing the game, teenagers were able to inform us about their feel towards visiting their incarcerated father. More specifically, we got a more precise view of how mixed emotions pertaining to visiting situations in prison may conflict with each other. How emotional conflicts evoke different kinds of action tendencies and uncomfortable interactions. By accounting for this, we hope to have shown how design activism can find its way to the Design & Emotion research community.

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